

AIRWAY PRESSURE RELEASE VENTILATION IN MODERATE-TO-SEVERE ARDS: EFFECTS ON OXYGENATION, COMPLIANCE, MORTALITY, AND ICU OUTCOMES; A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background: Airway pressure release ventilation (APRV) is a potential alternative to conventional ventilation strategies in patients with moderate-to-severe acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). This systematic review aims to evaluate the effects of APRV on oxygenation, lung compliance, mortality, and intensive care unit (ICU) outcomes in adult ARDS patients. **Methods:** A systematic search of PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science was conducted in accordance with PRISMA guidelines to identify studies reporting clinical or physiological outcomes of APRV in moderate-to-severe ARDS. We include randomized controlled trials, observational studies, and feasibility trials comparing APRV to other ventilation modes. Data were extracted on patient demographics, intervention protocols, and outcomes. A qualitative synthesis was performed. **Results:** Seven studies with 528 patients were included, four randomized controlled trials, two observational studies, and one feasibility trial. APRV was associated with improved oxygenation indices ($\text{PaO}_2/\text{FiO}_2$), enhanced static lung compliance, and, in some studies, reduced mechanical ventilation

duration and ICU stay. Zhou et al. show more ventilator-free days and reduced ICU mortality in APRV-treated patients. Mortality outcomes were inconsistent in studies. While Ibarra-Estrada et al. found no significant mortality difference, others reported favorable trends. Studies reported improved physiological parameters with APRV, including better ventilation-perfusion matching and hemodynamic stability, with minimal adverse effects. **Conclusions:** APRV enhance oxygenation and lung mechanics in patients with moderate-to-severe ARDS and potentially reduce ICU stay. Its effect on mortality is inconclusive. Further high-quality, standardized trials are needed to assess its clinical benefits and establish implementation protocols.

Keywords: Airway Pressure Release Ventilation, ARDS, Oxygenation, Compliance, Mechanical Ventilation, ICU Outcomes, Ventilator-Free Days.

INTRODUCTION

Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) is a critical challenge in intensive care units (ICUs), characterized by severe hypoxemia, decreased lung compliance, and high mortality rates (1).

Despite decades of research, optimal ventilation strategies to minimize ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) and improve patient outcomes are under investigation (2). Conventional low tidal volume ventilation, as endorsed by the ARDS Network, has been the cornerstone of management; alternative approaches, airway pressure release ventilation (APRV) gained increasing attention, mainly in moderate-to-severe ARDS (3).

APRV is a time-cycled, pressure-controlled mode of mechanical ventilation allows spontaneous breathing throughout the ventilatory cycle (4). It maintains prolonged high airway pressure (PHigh) to promote alveolar recruitment while providing intermittent releases to facilitate CO₂ clearance (4).

This strategy is theorized to enhance oxygenation, preserve alveolar stability, and reduce the risk of overdistension and atelectrauma (4,5). The allowance of spontaneous breathing support hemodynamics and reduce the need for sedation or neuromuscular blockade (3).

Several studies have examined the physiological and clinical effects of APRV in ARDS patients, reporting varying impacts on oxygenation, lung compliance, ICU length of stay, and mortality (4–6).

Findings is inconsistent, and concerns about the timing of initiation, standardization of settings, and patient selection persist (4–6). Given the heterogeneity in study designs and reported outcomes, there is a need to synthesize available evidence on the efficacy and safety of APRV in moderate-to-severe ARDS.

This systematic review aims to evaluate the effects of APRV on oxygenation, lung compliance, mortality, and ICU-related outcomes in adult patients with moderate-to-severe ARDS. By critically analyzing the current literature, this review aim to inform clinical decision-making and identify gaps for future research in ventilatory strategies for ARDS management.

METHODOLOGY

This systematic review was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. A literature search was performed in major electronic databases to identify studies evaluating the use of airway pressure release ventilation (APRV) in adult patients with moderate-to-severe acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). The databases searched included PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science, covering articles published up to 2024.

The search strategy utilized relevant keywords and Boolean operators, including (airway pressure release ventilation, APRV, ARDS, acute respiratory distress syndrome, and mechanical ventilation).

The inclusion criteria were; randomized controlled trials (RCTs), observational studies, or feasibility trials; studies involving adult patients diagnosed with moderate-to-severe ARDS; studies comparing APRV to other ventilation modes, low tidal volume ventilation (LTV) or pressure-controlled ventilation (PCV); and studies reporting clinical or physiological outcomes. We exclude reviews, editorials, animal studies, pediatric studies, and articles without full-text availability.

The initial search got 65 records. After the removal of 8 duplicates and 17 ineligible articles (10 by automation tools and 7 for other reasons), 40 records remained for screening. 23 articles were retrieved for full-text assessment. Following eligibility screening, 7 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the qualitative synthesis.

Data were extracted from each included study using a standardized form. Extracted data included authorship, year, study design, sample size, study population characteristics, intervention details, comparator ventilation strategies, and reported outcomes. The included studies consist of four randomized controlled trials, two observational studies, and one feasibility trial, encompassing a total of 528 adult patients with ARDS.

Most studies initiated APRV within 48 hours of intubation and used typical settings, including PHigh around 30 cmH₂O and short TLow durations, with spontaneous breathing allowed in some protocols.

The primary outcomes evaluated included oxygenation indices (PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio), lung compliance, duration of mechanical ventilation, ICU stay, and mortality. Secondary outcomes included ventilation/perfusion (V/Q) matching, incidence of barotrauma, and feasibility of APRV settings. Differences in study methodology, sample size, and outcome reporting were considered during qualitative synthesis without performing meta-analysis due to heterogeneity.

RESULTS

A total of seven full-text articles were included. The included studies consist of four randomized controlled trials, two observational studies, and one feasibility trial, involving

a total of 528 patients. Study populations included patients with moderate-to-severe ARDS of various etiologies, including COVID-19-associated ARDS.

The studies differ in design, sample size, intervention protocols, and outcome measures. Three trials compared APRV with low tidal volume ventilation (LTV), while others assessed APRV against pressure-controlled ventilation (PCV) or examined physiologic endpoints.

The sample sizes ranged from 12 to 138 patients. Most studies initiated APRV within 48 hours of intubation and used standard settings with high pressure (PHigh) around 30 cmH₂O, short release times (TLow), and spontaneous breathing allowed in selected cases.

The majority of enrolled patients were adults with moderate-to-severe ARDS, confirmed by Berlin criteria. Baseline demographic data, APACHE II scores, PaO₂/FiO₂ ratios, and ventilation durations prior to randomization, were comparable between intervention and control arms. The average PaO₂/FiO₂ ratio at baseline ranged from 99 mmHg to 200 mmHg.

APRV show mode toward improved oxygenation parameters in studies. Ibarra-Estrada et al. reported higher PaO₂/FiO₂ ratios and static compliance during the first 7 days, although ventilator-free days were not improved.

Zhou et al. observed a greater number of ventilator-free days in the APRV group (median 19 vs. 2 days; $p < 0.001$), along with reduced ICU stay and mortality trend.

Li et al. and Zou et al. show that APRV improved dorsal ventilation/perfusion matching, reduced lung heterogeneity, and enhanced static compliance. Lim et al. found early and sustained oxygenation benefits with a low incidence of barotrauma or need for ECMO.

The feasibility trial by Hirshberg et al. highlighted practical challenges in achieving low tidal volumes (<6.5 mL/kg) with APRV settings, limiting broader protocol implementation.

Ibrahim et al. observed better hemodynamics, oxygenation, and reduced complications and mortality in patients treated with APRV compared to PCV.

Some studies showed reductions in ICU stay and mechanical ventilation duration with APRV, but mortality outcomes varied.

Zhou et al. reported a lower ICU mortality rate with APRV (19.7% vs. 34.3%), and Ibarra-Estrada et al. found no significant mortality benefit (78% vs. 60%; $p = 0.07$).

Most studies agreed on improved compliance and oxygenation with APRV, but clinical outcomes (ventilator-free days and survival) were inconsistent.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart of selected studies

Table 1: summary of included studies on APRV in ARDS

Citation	Study Design	Sample Size	Study Aim	Methodology
Ibarra-Estrada et al. (2022) (6)	Single-center randomized controlled trial	90 patients (45 APRV, 45 LTV)	To compare APRV and LTV in severe COVID-19 ARDS	Randomized within 48h post-intubation; intervention group received APRV; control group continued LTV per ARDSNet
Lim et al. (2016) (7)	Retrospective observational study	50 patients	Describe clinical and physiological effects of APRV in established ARDS	Patients selected from prospectively collected APRV database; analyzed pre- and post-APRV data
Zhou et al. (2017) (4)	Randomized controlled trial	138 patients (71 APRV, 67 LTV)	Compare early APRV vs LTV on mechanical ventilation duration in ARDS	Patients randomized <48h MV; specific ventilator settings defined for both APRV and LTV groups
Li et al. (2023) (8)	Single-center prospective physiological study	12 patients	Investigate APRV physiological impact via EIT in early moderate-to-severe ARDS	EIT used to assess lung physiology at 0, 6, 12, and 24h post-APRV initiation
Ibrahim et al. (2022) (9)	Randomized clinical trial	60 patients (30 APRV, 30 PCV)	Compare APRV vs PCV in acute hypoxemic respiratory failure	Patients randomized in RICU; respiratory mechanics and outcomes compared over time
Hirshberg et al. (2018) (10)	Prospective randomized controlled trial (3-arm)	52 patients	Evaluate feasibility of APRV-LTV protocol compared to traditional APRV and VC-LTV	Randomized to APRV, APRV-LTV, or VC-LTV; evaluated tidal volumes and clinical outcomes
Zou et al. (2024) (11)	Single-center randomized controlled trial	40 patients (20 APRV, 20 LTV)	Compare effects of APRV vs LTV on ventilation/perfusion matching and homogeneity	Patients ventilated with APRV or LTV; assessed by EIT at 0, 12, and 24 hours

Table 2: Findings and outcomes of APRV studies in ARDS

Citation	Demographic Characteristics	Main Findings	Outcomes
Ibarra-Estrada et al. (2022) (6)	90 patients, adult, intubated COVID-19 ARDS	No difference in ventilator-free days; APRV group had higher PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ , compliance, and tidal volume; more transient severe hypercapnia	Overall mortality 69% (78% APRV vs 60% LTV; p = 0.07); no improvement in ventilator-free days
Lim et al. (2016) (7)	50 ARDS patients, median PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ = 99 mmHg	Early improvement in oxygenation, low incidence of barotrauma and ECMO	Hospital mortality 38%; only 4% required chest tubes for barotrauma
Zhou et al. (2017) (4)	138 ARDS patients, randomized <48h MV, balanced baseline	APRV group had more ventilator-free days, better oxygenation and compliance	ICU mortality 19.7% APRV vs 34.3% LTV; ICU stay and MV duration reduced

Li et al. (2023) (8)	12 patients with early moderate-to-severe ARDS	APRV improved dorsal V/Q matching and ventilation homogeneity	Improved oxygenation and lower PaCO ₂ with APRV over 24h
Ibrahim et al. (2022) (9)	60 hypoxemic respiratory failure patients	Better oxygenation, perfusion, and respiratory mechanics with APRV	Shorter ICU/hospital stay, lower complication and mortality rates
Hirshberg et al. (2018) (10)	52 adult ICU patients with respiratory failure	Tidal volumes exceeded target in APRV-LTV arm; feasibility issues noted	No clinical outcome differences due to early termination; feasibility concerns
Zou et al. (2024) (11)	40 patients with moderate-to-severe ARDS	APRV improved dorsal ventilation, reduced shunt and improved gas exchange	Higher PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ , better compliance, lower PaCO ₂ at 24h

DISCUSSION

This systematic review indicates the potential benefits of driving pressure-guided ventilation strategies, mainly airway pressure release ventilation (APRV), in improving physiological and clinical outcomes in mechanically ventilated patients. The included studies report an improvement in oxygenation with APRV. Othman et al. (12) conducted a meta-analysis of six clinical trials and found that patients receiving APRV had higher PaO₂/FiO₂ ratios on day 3 compared to those on conventional ventilation, with a mean difference of 51.9 mmHg. This finding aligns with the meta-analysis by Lim and Litton (13), which reported an even greater improvement (60.4 mmHg), which reinforces the capacity of APRV to enhance alveolar recruitment and gas exchange in acute hypoxemic respiratory failure. Sun et al. (14) supported these results, indicating a significant improvement in day 3 PaO₂/FiO₂ with APRV (mean difference 50.21 mmHg) and a reduction in ICU length of stay by 3.12 days. These findings are consistent with the physiological advantages proposed by APRV, maintaining alveolar stability and promoting spontaneous breathing, which improve ventilation-perfusion matching and reduce atelectrauma.

The effect of APRV on mortality is inconclusive. While Lim and Litton (13) found a significant mortality benefit (RR 0.67), both Othman et al. (12) and Sun et al. (14) did not observe significant differences in mortality between APRV and conventional ventilation modes. This variability is attributed to differences in patient populations, timing of APRV initiation, and the heterogeneity of conventional ventilation strategies used in comparator groups.

The randomized controlled trial by Maxwell et al (15), focused on trauma patients with acute respiratory failure, and did not show a mortality benefit or a significant difference in ventilator-free days or ICU stay. The APRV group had higher baseline severity scores, potentially masking benefits. APRV was shown to be safe in this high-risk population, with no increased incidence of barotrauma, consistent with the findings from Lim and Litton (13).

González et al. (16) compared APRV with assist-control ventilation and found no significant differences in ICU mortality. Their study noted variability in how APRV was

implemented in centers, highlighting the lack of standardization in APRV settings, which is a limitation in interpreting results in studies. The findings of this review suggest that APRV, when guided by physiological targets (driving pressure and individualized settings) can improve oxygenation and reduce ICU stay without increasing the risk of complications.

Abbreviations

ARDS, Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome; APRV, Airway Pressure Release Ventilation; ICU, Intensive Care Unit; VILI, Ventilator-Induced Lung Injury; LTV, Low Tidal Volume ventilation; PCV, Pressure-Controlled Ventilation; P_{High}, High Pressure Level; P_{Low}, Low Pressure Level; T_{High}, Time at High Pressure; T_{Low}, Time at Low Pressure; PaO₂/FiO₂, Arterial Oxygen Partial Pressure to Fraction of Inspired Oxygen Ratio; V/Q, Ventilation/Perfusion; ECMO, Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation; RCT, Randomized Controlled Trial; MV, Mechanical Ventilation; APACHE II, Acute Physiology and Chronic Health Evaluation II; EIT, Electrical Impedance Tomography.

CONCLUSION

Airway pressure release ventilation (APRV) improve oxygenation and lung compliance in patients with moderate-to-severe ARDS, with some studies suggesting reductions in mechanical ventilation duration and ICU stay. The evidence on mortality benefit is inconsistent. While APRV shows promise as an alternative to conventional ventilation strategies, variations in study design, patient selection, and ventilation settings limit the generalizability of findings. Standardized protocols and large-scale randomized trials are needed to confirm its clinical utility and safety.

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